

Innovative E-Motor Technologies for E-Axles and E-Corners Vehicle Architectures Enabling Highly Efficient and Sustainable E-Mobility

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Abstract. The Horizon Europe projects EM-TECH and HighScape propose innovative solutions for electric traction machines and their WBG-based drives and components, to achieve higher energy efficiency, reduced volume and mass, as well as reduced cost. This paper outlines the main innovations of EM-TECH and HighScape, targeting a wide range of vehicle applications, including passenger cars and commercial vehicles. Specifically, EM-TECH deals with: i) modular designs of on-board axial flux machines (AFMs) for reducing the implementation costs of scalable centralised powertrains for electric axle (e-Axle) solutions; ii) in-wheel motors (IWMs) integrated with electric gearing, for expanding the high efficiency region of electric corner (e-Corner) powertrains; and iii) the use of permanent magnets deriving from recycling processes to improve sustainability. In parallel, HighScape targets the physical and functional integration of the

power electronics of WBG-based traction inverters, onboard chargers, DC/DC converters, and electric drives for auxiliaries and actuators.

Keywords: in-wheel motors · axial-flux motors · electric gears · wide bandgap power electronics

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe topics CL5–2022-D5–01-09 and CL5–2021-D5–01-02 target innovations in two key areas of next-generation electric vehicles (EVs): the advancement of electric motors (e-Motors), and the promotion of the wide bandgap (WBG) based power electronics (PE) technologies (SiC, GaN, and beyond).

Within this context, the project “Innovative e-Motor technologies covering e-Axle and e-Corner vehicle architectures for highly efficient and sustainable e-Mobility” (EM-TECH) addresses innovative machine solutions with the following main objectives: i) increasing the primary efficiency of electric traction machines, namely 35% energy loss reduction for direct drive in-wheel machines (IWMs) for electric corners (e-Corners), and 25% reduction for on-board axial flux machines (AFMs) for electric axles (e-Axles), with respect to (w.r.t.) state-of-the-art (SoA) machines, during realistic driving cycles; ii) obtaining high torque density and specific torque values ($> 150 \text{ Nm/L}$ and $> 50 \text{ Nm/kg}$) for IWMs, and high power density and specific power ($> 30 \text{ kW/L}$ and 10 kW/kg for AFMs); iii) achieving production costs of $< 6 \text{ Euro/kW}$ for IWMs and 5 Euro/kW for AFMs (assuming $> 100\text{k}$ yearly units); iv) facilitating circularity solutions with $> 60\%$ reduction in the use of rare earth resources. Concurrently, the project “High efficiency, high power density, cost effective, scalable and modular power electronics and control solutions for electric vehicles” (HighScape) aims at innovative PE solutions with the following goals: i) scalable WBG-based PE components, with so far unexplored levels of functional integration in IWMs, battery systems, and auxiliaries/chassis actuators; ii) improved power density, resulting in $> 100 \text{ kW/L}$ and $> 80\%$ reduction of component volume w.r.t. existing Si-based solutions; iii) enhanced energy efficiency (up to 99%), and thermal management of the resulting PE components; iv) $> 35\%$ production cost reduction w.r.t. the available WBG-based PE products and prototypes; v) improvements in functional safety, fault-tolerance, predictive maintenance, and electro-magnetic interference (EMI) and electro-magnetic compatibility (EMC) performance.

This paper focuses on a few highlights of the activities that EM-TECH and HighScape, sharing a significant number of consortium participants, will carry out in the next 2 years, and outlines the respective innovative solutions for e-Motors and PE.

2 Innovative e-Machine Solutions

2.1 Axial-Flux e-Motor for e-Axle Applications

Table 1 reports examples of SoA e-Motors for EVs. Axial flux configurations (Yasa, Magnax) can bring significantly higher performance in comparison to the established radial flux motor implementations currently available in the market (e.g., those of the

Volkswagen ID.3, BMW i3, and Tesla Model 3). Recent advances in AFMs have been presented in the literature [1], and further improvements have been demonstrated by the EM-TECH participants (in particular, by Vaionic Technologies) prior to the project kick-off, thanks to the proof-of-concept introduction of ground-breaking innovations, namely iron-less stators, leading to: i) the absence of iron losses, which typically dominate in driving cycles like the WLTP; ii) reduced bearing losses, because of the minimal axial forces; and iii) NVH improvements, due to the decreased torque ripple and acoustic noise. To make the baseline Vaionic AFM solution mature across various vehicle segments, the EM-TECH project will pursue four crucial improvements: i) the development of a scalable design methodology; ii) the introduction of a Halbach array permanent magnet (PM) configuration to improve the flux density; iii) the use of PMs deriving from recycling processes, and implementation of the corresponding life cycle assessment (LCA); and iv) virtual sensing of PM temperature to reduce the design and operation conservativeness. Notably, items iii) and iv) are being carried out with a methodological approach also applicable to the EM-TECH IWMs.

Table 1. Characteristics of state-of-the-art on-board e-Machines for EVs, and the proposed EM-TECH solution by Vaionic.

	VW ID.3	BMW i3	Tesla Model 3	Yasa R400 P	Magnax AXF 250	Vaionic
Topology	Radial flux	Radial flux	Radial flux	Axial flux	Axial flux	Axial flux
Iron-less stator	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Mass (kg)	40	46 ¹	47	28	25 ¹	24
Cont. Power (kW)	60	75	100	100	n.d	250
Cont. Specific power (kW/kg)	1.5	1.6	2.1	3.5	n.d	10.4
Max. Speed (rpm)	16,000	12,000	18,000	8,000	12,000	20,000

¹ Without housing

2.2 In-Wheel Motor with e-Gear for e-Corner Applications

EM-TECH will carry out a simulation-based optimisation of the baseline L1500 motor unit by Elaphe, one of the EM-TECH participants. The IWM unit is characterised by 1500 Nm peak torque, 1670 rpm maximum speed, 45 Nm/kg specific torque, 114 kW peak power, and 3.4 kW/kg specific power. Moreover, the consortium will design an

innovative system with electric gears (e-Gears) through motor's winding reconfiguration, which will significantly extend its high-efficiency operating region. Previous work by Oak Ridge National Laboratory [2] suggested a costly e-Gear solution based on five antiparallel thyristors (1600V/120A at ~ 20 € each, or 1600V/240A at ~ 40€ each). The EM-TECH 2-speed e-Gear concept exploits a mechanical switching system as working principle. This offers a feasible route to achieve the cost requirement and extend this technology through the mainstream market of automotive applications. One of the key challenges in the mechanical design will be to achieve low electrical resistance between the switch contacts, without excessive mechanical clamping force. As well as traditional flat contacts, a variety of alternative solutions will be investigated, including conical contacts and lamellar contacts. The electric gearshift will unavoidably add cost to the system if all other parts remain unchanged. However, by developing and demonstrating a mechanical solution with a single actuator, it is expected that the cost will be considerably less than that of alternative solutions, such as solid-state semiconductor implementations or 2-speed mechanical transmissions. In contrast, the mechanical switching setup uses widely available materials and inexpensive manufacturing techniques. Thus, it has excellent potential for cost optimisation, either by downsizing the machine, which reduces usage of high-value magnetic materials, or by downgrading the PE in the inverter to lower current ratings.

2.3 Direct Cooling and Virtual Sensing

In EM-TECH, disruptive e-Motor improvements will be achieved through multiple solutions based on direct liquid cooling slots in the stator lamination, cooling slot channels, and wet stator cooling. Each of them has a strong impact on the mechanical layout, packaging, and manufacturing process of the machine. Concurrently with the hardware optimisation, real-time measurements and estimates of key electrical and mechanical quantities, i.e., voltage commands, phase currents and DC-link voltage signals, back EMF (electromotive force), torque and speed, together with the temperatures in key stator locations, will be used for the real-time prediction and monitoring of the temperature distribution within the PMs. In this area, past research efforts have been focusing on state observers. To overcome the drawbacks of model-based techniques, in EM-TECH novel artificial-intelligence (AI) based approaches will be developed and implemented, to guarantee fast execution times and adaptability to multiple input signal combinations. Unsupervised and supervised learning will be compared to yield robust solutions able to respond to variable working conditions, including transients of the electrical, mechanical and thermal variables. At the same time, EM-TECH will address the efficient integration of these algorithms onto conventional digital signal processors for motor control.

3 Innovative PE Solutions

The HighScope architectural solution only includes two or four IWMs (depending on the two- or four-wheel-drive nature of the specific EV) and an integrated high voltage (HV) battery, i.e., all PE components are physically incorporated into these two major building blocks (with the potential exception of the filter towards the grid), at a level never seen in

any previous EV implementation. Also, from a functional perspective, the PE parts are used for multiple purposes whenever possible, across the IWMs and HV battery, with major benefits in terms of cost as well as power density and specific power, since the “overhead” parts disappear. Figure 1 a) is the schematic of the HighScope PE concept. The on-board charger (OBC), traction inverter and accessory DC/DC converter will be functionally integrated, with significant cost reduction and major power density increase, thanks to a substantial reduction of the number of components, and the replacement of the Si-based power modules with the WBG equivalents (SiC and/or. GaN), enabling higher switching frequencies and temperatures. The galvanically isolated integrated OBC will be implemented by using the SiC power MOSFETs of one of the traction drives, with the coils of one of the IWMs that are “re-used” as boost inductors. The dual-active full-bridge converter is placed within the battery, as this is the converter that adapts the voltage and current needed to charge the battery from the DC voltage created by the PFC (power factor conversion) circuit, which consists of the traction drive components. The transformer of the high voltage converter will be designed to also enable a conversion to a much lower voltage, and create the charger function for the 12V battery and accessory circuits. The EMI filters for the grid inlet, 3-phase or 1-phase, will be placed close together to enhance the system packaging. The traction motor will have the inverter as well as the PFC circuit of the OBC incorporated in some of the existing cavities in the IWM housing, while all the other PE components will be incorporated in the battery pack. Figure 1 b), c) and d) illustrate three operating modes of the highly integrated PE systems: battery charging, traction mode, and vehicle-to-grid connection.

Fig. 1. The HighScope integrated PE architecture concept (a), with three operating modes (b-d).

4 Vehicle Level Control Functions

Given the absence of the drivetrain torsional dynamics and mechanical plays, direct drive IWMs can provide significantly higher wheel torque responsiveness and bandwidth than typical on-board powertrains, as well as more accurate wheel torque actuation. It

is estimated that the new IWM drives will have a rise time of less than 10 ms for a step torque demand. This will be exploited for new control functions at the vehicle level. For example, the new IWMs will provide faster dynamic response than conventional friction brake actuators, and therefore could be adopted for anti-lock braking system (ABS) torque modulation. During ABS events, the friction brakes would provide only the low-frequency component of the braking torque. This idea has been mentioned and preliminarily assessed in a proof-of-concept analysis by Toyota [3], but it has never been systematically implemented, also for the lack of IWMs meeting the industrialisation requirements for passenger cars, which will be covered by EM-TECH and HighScope. Similar benefits could be achieved during traction control operation. In parallel, tyre-road friction preview for wheel slip control, which could be achieved through future vehicle-to-everything (V2X) implementations, will be evaluated, according to the initial promising study in [4], focused on sudden variations of the friction coefficient during longitudinal acceleration tests. Fast modulation of the IWM torque can be also used to dampen the longitudinal vehicle body acceleration oscillations caused by the road irregularities, and thus improve the drivability. In this respect, a preliminary simulation study has been presented in [5]. Within HighScope and EM-TECH, a first proof-of-concept experimental implementation will be carried out.

From a methodological viewpoint, nonlinear model predictive control (MPC) solutions will be adapted to the control of the new electric drives, and expanded to include neural network (NN) technologies, which will result into neural network model predictive control. For example, the NNs will be used for capturing the nonlinear dynamics that are difficult to model analytically, e.g., the effect of the uncertain tyre-road friction coefficient. The activity will focus on: i) exploring the achievable vehicle performance impact of IWM settings with different levels of responsiveness; and ii) providing robust controllers that could be further industrialised at project completion.

5 Virtual and Experimental Testing

The EM-TECH and HighScope verification and validation environment will consist of: i) a set of models of e-Machines, powertrains and full vehicles, including real-time reduced-order models, together with a functional mock-up interface (FMI) for co-simulation; ii) connected Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) platforms for the assessment of motor/inverter and vehicle controllers, and other relevant controllable hardware components, including EV systems that require a joint operation with the e-Machine, e.g., for regenerative braking; and iii) dynamometric testing setups to emulate the operation of electric propulsion units in laboratory conditions under real load and speed cycles. This constellation of tools will enable flexible testing as part of a digital twin development process to perform functional and life cycle analyses of the new IWMs, AFMs, and PE components. The XiL (X-in-the-Loop) verification of the components and systems will be complemented by testing on the project EV demonstrators, represented by modified versions of production vehicles of the involved car makers (AUDI and TOFAŞ).

6 Conclusion

This paper has outlined the planned developments of the Horizon Europe EM-TECH and HighScape projects. The innovations will result in new in-wheel machines with so far unexplored levels of torque density and specific torque ($> 150 \text{ Nm/L}$, $> 50 \text{ Nm/kg}$), and on-board axial flux machines with high power density and specific power ($> 30 \text{ kW/L}$, $> 10 \text{ kW/kg}$). Both machine technologies will be characterised by significant reductions of the energy losses and their rare earth content. As a result, it will be possible to reach the competitive production costs of $< 6 \text{ Euro/kW}$ for IWMs and 5 Euro/kW for AFMs, for yearly volumes $> 100\text{k}$ units. For the new WBG-based traction inverter solutions, $> 80\%$ size reduction and $> 60\%$ average power loss decreases w.r.t. Si-based solutions are expected.

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